

Application of New Polyvitamins in A- And D-Hypovitaminosis Deficiency in Young Calves

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Abstract: *This article examines the effectiveness of new polyvitamin preparations in the prevention and correction of A- and D-hypovitaminosis in young calves. The study focuses on the impact of feeding dairy cows with the nutritional supplement Renomix on calf development, resistance to diseases, and metabolic stability. Experimental results indicate that calves born from cows supplemented with Renomix demonstrated improved biochemical blood parameters, normalization of metabolic processes, and increased physiological activity. Adequate vitamin supply contributed to enhanced immune resistance, prevention of growth retardation, and reduced susceptibility to respiratory and digestive disorders. The findings confirm that polyvitamin supplementation plays a significant role in maintaining homeostasis and improving overall health in young calves. The application of safe and effective polyvitamin preparations is therefore considered an essential preventive and therapeutic strategy in veterinary practice to reduce economic losses associated with hypovitaminosis and metabolic disorders in cattle farming.*

Keywords: *Young calves, hypovitaminosis A, hypovitaminosis D, polyvitamins, Renomix, metabolism, biochemical parameters.*

Relevance and Necessity of the Study

In veterinary practice, the use of new, highly effective, and safe pharmaceutical preparations is of great importance, as metabolic disorders—particularly hypovitaminosis—in young animals lead to growth retardation, decreased natural resistance, and increased susceptibility to various diseases, resulting in significant economic losses in cattle farms [1]. Vitamin A deficiency in animals is characterized by dryness of the skin and mucous membranes, decreased skin elasticity, rough hair coat, alopecia, impaired growth, respiratory and digestive diseases, conjunctivitis, hemeralopia, xerophthalmia, reproductive disorders, embryonic abortions, retained placenta, and reduced overall resistance of the organism. These conditions necessitate the use of polyvitamin and mineral preparations. Therefore, studying the therapeutic and preventive effects of polyvitamins on metabolic disorders in animals remains a relevant and urgent issue [2-3].

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this research was to pharmacotherapeutically evaluate the effectiveness of polyvitamin preparations in calves affected by A- and D-hypovitaminosis [4].

Objectives of the Study

To develop methods for the treatment and group prevention of A- and D-hypovitaminosis in calves using polyvitamin preparations.

Research Objects

The research objects included calves raised in cattle-breeding farms of Qiziltepa district, Navoi region, as well as blood samples obtained from these animals.

Research Methods

Clinical, morphological, biochemical, microscopic examination methods, and statistical data processing techniques were used to diagnose A- and D-hypovitaminosis in calves.

Scientific Novelty of the Study

It was determined that during the first month of lactation, the concentration of retinol in cow's milk was, on average, 0.42 µg% lower than the physiological norm, while the level of tocopherol was reduced by an average of 0.5 µg%. In addition, total calcium content was found to be decreased by 7 mg%. A deficiency of reproductive vitamins was also recorded, which may negatively affect reproductive performance and metabolic stability [5].

Practical Results of the Study

The study scientifically substantiated the characteristic clinical, morphological, and hemobiochemical changes observed in calves affected by A- and D-hypovitaminosis. The obtained results provide a practical basis for early diagnosis, prevention, and correction of hypovitaminosis-related metabolic disorders in young calves under farm conditions [6-7].

Reliability of the Research Results

The reliability of the research findings is ensured by the use of modern investigative methods and tools, including hemomorphological and hemobiochemical analyses, appropriate processing of primary data, and consistency between theoretical conclusions and experimental results.

Chemical Composition and Biological Properties of Colostrum and Milk Fed to Calves

The chemical composition and biological characteristics of colostrum and milk fed to calves were evaluated. The acidity of colostrum, measured in Turner degrees, averaged $25.2 \pm 1.2^{\circ}\text{T}$ on the first day after calving (normal value: 39.9°T), $20.5 \pm 1.3^{\circ}\text{T}$ on the fifth day, and $22.4 \pm 1.6^{\circ}\text{T}$ on the eighth day [8-9].

Similarly, the fat content of colostrum averaged $3.1 \pm 0.8\%$ on the first day, $2.8 \pm 0.22\%$ on the fifth day, and $2.7 \pm 0.34\%$ on the eighth day.

Chemical Composition of Colostrum Fed to Calves

Indicators	Days after calving
	Day 1
Acidity, °T	25.2 ± 1.2
Fat, %	3.1 ± 0.8
Protein, %	10.8 ± 1.24
Milk sugar (lactose), %	3.1 ± 0.17
Dry matter, %	16.8 ± 1.52

α -tocopherol, $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = \text{CH}_3$
 α -tocotrienol, $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = \text{CH}_3$

γ -tocopherol, $R_1 = R_2 = \text{CH}_3$ $R_3 = \text{H}$
 γ -tocotrienol, $R_1 = R_2 = \text{CH}_3$ $R_3 = \text{H}$

β -tocopherol, $R_1 = R_3 = \text{CH}_3$; $R_2 = \text{H}$
 β -tocotrienol, $R_1 = R_3 = \text{CH}_3$; $R_2 = \text{H}$

δ -tocopherol, $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = \text{H}$
 δ -tocotrienol, $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = \text{H}$

Vitamin E (Tocopherol)

The vitamin content of milk from cows in Farm 1 was characterized by a relatively reduced level. The concentration of retinol during the first month of lactation averaged $0.96 \pm 0.02 \mu\text{g}\%$, while in the third month of lactation it was $0.72 \pm 0.03 \mu\text{g}\%$. In cows from Farm 2, the retinol content of milk was $0.88 \pm 0.05 \mu\text{g}\%$ and $0.65 \pm 0.04 \mu\text{g}\%$ during the first and third months of lactation, respectively [10-11].

The content of vitamin E (tocopherol) in the milk of cows from Farm 1 averaged $8.2 \pm 0.07 \mu\text{g}\%$ in the first month of lactation and $7.5 \pm 0.06 \mu\text{g}\%$ in the third month. In Farm 2, the tocopherol content was correspondingly $8.4 \pm 0.05 \mu\text{g}\%$ and $7.3 \pm 0.04 \mu\text{g}\%$.

Hematological and Biochemical Parameters During Treatment of A-Hypovitaminosis in Calves

During experiments aimed at treating A-hypovitaminosis, blood samples were collected from affected calves at the beginning of treatment and subsequently every ten days for laboratory analysis. Calves in the control group were fed according to the standard farm ration [12].

In the control group, the erythrocyte count in blood samples averaged 4.83 ± 0.02 million/ μL at the beginning of treatment, 4.82 ± 0.05 million/ μL on day 10, 4.80 ± 0.07 million/ μL on day 20, and 4.79 ± 0.09 million/ μL on day 30 (reference range: 5.0–7.5 million/ μL).

The leukocyte count averaged 7.17 ± 2.27 thousand/ μL at the beginning, 7.25 ± 0.45 thousand/ μL on day 10, 7.32 ± 0.61 thousand/ μL on day 20, and 7.24 ± 0.12 thousand/ μL on day 30 (reference range: 4.5–12.0 thousand/ μL).

Hemoglobin concentration averaged 97.2 ± 3.58 g/L at the beginning of treatment, 96.8 ± 2.84 g/L on day 10, 96.9 ± 2.71 g/L on day 20, and 96.6 ± 2.12 g/L on day 30 (reference range: 99–129 g/L) [13].

Blood glucose concentration averaged 2.17 ± 0.06 mmol/L at the beginning, 2.16 ± 0.03 mmol/L on day 10, 2.18 ± 0.05 mmol/L on day 20, and 2.20 ± 0.07 mmol/L on day 30 (reference range: 2.22–3.33 mmol/L).

Total protein concentration averaged 62.28 ± 3.31 g/L at the beginning of treatment, 62.56 ± 2.46 g/L on day 10, 63.47 ± 0.54 g/L on day 20, and 65.14 ± 4.72 g/L on day 30 (reference range: 72.0–86.0 g/L).

Retinol concentration averaged $11.48 \pm 2.24 \mu\text{g}\%$ at the beginning of treatment, $11.66 \pm 3.47 \mu\text{g}\%$ on day 10, $11.87 \pm 5.75 \mu\text{g}\%$ on day 20, and $12.49 \pm 4.42 \mu\text{g}\%$ on day 30 (reference range: 16.2–18.4 $\mu\text{g}\%$) [14].

Carotene concentration averaged 0.27 ± 0.04 mg% at the beginning, 0.27 ± 0.07 mg% on day 10, 0.29 ± 0.08 mg% on day 20, and 0.30 ± 0.04 mg% on day 30 (reference range: 0.1–1.0 mg%). The observed differences were statistically significant ($P < 0.001$; $P < 0.01$; $P < 0.05$) [15].

Morphobiochemical Blood Parameters During Prevention of A-Hypovitaminosis in Calves

(Mukhammadali Kelajagi Farm; M ± m; N = 9)

Groups	Prevention period, days	Erythrocytes, million/ μ L	Hemoglobin, g/L	Glucose, mmol/L	Total protein, g/L	Retinol, μ g%	Leukocytes, thousand/ μ L	Carotene, mg%
Control (I)	Initial	4.81 ± 0.04	94.56 ± 2.34	2.13 ± 0.02	63.51 ± 3.66	11.67 ± 2.34	7.81 ± 2.47	0.29 ± 0.03
	30	4.83 ± 0.05	94.28 ± 2.67	2.13 ± 0.05	63.89 ± 2.27	11.95 ± 3.54	7.64 ± 5.74	0.28 ± 0.08
	60	4.79 ± 0.02	95.17 ± 2.43	2.14 ± 0.07	64.17 ± 2.74	12.22 ± 5.78	7.77 ± 2.31	0.31 ± 0.05
	90	4.80 ± 0.08	95.52 ± 5.88	2.16 ± 0.09	64.33 ± 4.28	14.37 ± 4.52	7.43 ± 5.19	0.32 ± 0.07
Experimenta I II	Initial	4.75 ± 0.05	92.45 ± 2.63	2.12 ± 0.09	62.76 ± 3.22	11.25 ± 2.33	6.75 ± 2.28	0.27 ± 0.08
	30	5.32 ± 0.02	99.57 ± 2.26	2.52 ± 0.04	73.35 ± 2.57	15.53 ± 3.46	6.70 ± 3.46	0.58 ± 0.04
	60	5.84 ± 0.08	112.34 ± 2.85	2.78 ± 0.07	77.84 ± 2.51	17.51 ± 4.71	6.82 ± 2.52	0.67 ± 0.06
	90	6.69 ± 0.04	116.56 ± 2.33	3.17 ± 0.02	82.93 ± 4.53	18.68 ± 4.48	6.89 ± 3.33	0.81 ± 0.05
Experimenta I III	Initial	4.79 ± 0.04	93.58 ± 2.47	2.13 ± 0.05	63.32 ± 3.76	11.46 ± 2.62	7.12 ± 2.55	0.28 ± 0.09
	30	5.14 ± 0.02	99.27 ± 2.34	2.38 ± 0.04	70.25 ± 2.47	15.29 ± 3.45	7.26 ± 3.41	0.44 ± 0.04
	60	5.96 ± 0.07	114.23 ± 2.58	2.62 ± 0.09	75.41 ± 4.50	16.25 ± 5.57	7.15 ± 2.48	0.57 ± 0.08
	90	6.57 ± 0.09	118.15 ± 2.45	2.92 ± 0.05	79.47 ± 3.55	17.53 ± 4.12	7.33 ± 4.29	0.66 ± 0.06

Statistical significance:

P < 0.01 (erythrocytes), P < 0.05 (hemoglobin), P < 0.01 (glucose), P < 0.05 (total protein), P < 0.001 (retinol), P < 0.01 (leukocytes), P < 0.01 (carotene).

Conclusion

The application of polyvitamin preparations for the prevention of A- and D-hypovitaminosis in calves resulted in significant improvements in hematological and biochemical parameters compared to the control group. Specifically, an increase was observed in erythrocyte count by 37.85%, hemoglobin concentration by 20.6%, blood glucose level by 26.38%, total serum protein by 25.45%, carotene concentration by 60.5%, retinol concentration by 31.24%, total calcium by 10.95%, and inorganic phosphorus by 38.75%. At the same time, a decrease in alkaline phosphatase enzyme activity by 51.3% was recorded. These changes indicate normalization of metabolic processes, improved vitamin–mineral status, and enhanced physiological stability of the organism. The results confirm the high preventive efficacy of polyvitamin supplementation in reducing hypovitaminosis-related metabolic disorders in calves.

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